

The Bi-O-Edge Wavefront Sensor: First Steps Toward Experimental Validation

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ABSTRACT

Fourier Filtering Wavefront Sensors (FFWS) are now widely used in eXtreme Adaptive Optics (XAO) to benefit from their high sensitivity, enabling operation on fainter targets or faster AO loop speeds. However, this gain in sensitivity is often associated with a reduced dynamic range. The sensor's dynamic range can be extended using different strategies (tip/tilt modulation, longer sensing wavelengths, multi-stage AO, smart reconstruction algorithms, etc.), but at the cost of increased operational complexity. In this communication, we investigate the Bi-O-Edge concept as a promising approach to perform high-sensitivity wavefront sensing while keeping an extended dynamic range. We present our progress towards the first experimental validation of the Bi-O-Edge on a prototype bench currently under development at the Laboratoire d'Astrophysique de Marseille (LAM). The technical implementation investigated here relies on a Patterned Liquid Crystal optical element that tunes the polarization of the incoming light, enabling amplitude-like fourier filtering with no photon loss.

Keywords: adaptive optics – wavefront sensing – Fourier-filtering – bi-o-edge – polarization – patterned liquid crystal array – Wollaston prism

1. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive Optics (AO) systems, first demonstrated for astronomy in the 1990s, are now becoming the baseline of ground-based observatories. Achieving eXtreme Adaptive Optics (XAO) performance requires sensitive wavefront sensors (WFS) — meaning capable of providing reliable measurements with fewer photons — to extend sky coverage or increase AO loop speed. Fourier filtering wavefront sensors, such as the pyramid wavefront sensor [7] — which is part of most Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) first-light instruments — exhibit high sensitivity, but at the cost of a limited dynamic range. In order to deploy the pyramid as a first-stage wavefront sensor under realistic turbulence conditions, one must broaden its dynamic range. This is classically achieved through tip/tilt modulation: by making the point spread function (PSF) rotate around the tip of the pyramid and incoherently averaging the signal over one exposure of the wavefront sensor, one can trade part of the pyramid sensitivity for a broader dynamic range.

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The Bi-O-Edge wavefront sensor (which stands for Bi-Orthogonal Edges), recently introduced by Verinaud et al. [10], is directly inspired by the modulated pyramid. Like the pyramid, it encodes wavefront phase via Foucault knife-edge filtering in the focal plane, and the linearity ranges of these two sensors are therefore expected to be comparable. However, Verinaud et al. have shown that circular tip/tilt modulation has a fundamental drawback: it prevents a fraction of the photons carrying phase information from contributing to the wavefront sensing signal, thereby reducing the sensitivity of the modulated pyramid. This circular tip/tilt modulation is replaced by a static focal-plane filtering in the Bi-O-Edge concept, providing a more efficient use of the photons and therefore enabling a more sensitive sensing.

This static filtering is achieved through a linear intensity transmission gradient in the focal plane (the so-called grey area). Several closely related concepts share this principle — such as the Optical Differentiation Wavefront Sensor (ODWFS) [6], the Phase Visualization (PV) sensor [5], or the G-ODWFS [2], which generalises both of the above. In these sensors, the grey area typically spans a large fraction of the focal plane. The key distinction of the Bi-O-Edge is that this grey area is deliberately kept narrow, spanning only a few diffraction diameters, so as to be comparable in extent to the modulation radius of a modulated pyramid wavefront sensor. This narrow grey area is what allows the Bi-O-Edge to simultaneously achieve a high sensitivity and an extended dynamic range.

In this paper, we present our progress towards the first experimental implementation of the Bi-O-Edge concept on a monochromatic test bench. The technical implementation of the Bi-O-Edge Fourier filtering that we choose to investigate is directly inspired by Haffert et al. [2], which provide a way to perform intensity-like focal plane filtering without losing photons. Our Bi-O-Edge mask prototype [11] is therefore based on the use of a Patterned Liquid Crystal optical element to tune the polarization of the light and enable amplitude-like filtering with no loss of photons. The use of such optical surfaces as Fourier filters for wavefront sensing has already been demonstrated on sky [3].

In section 2, we describe our experimental setup in detail. In section 3, we present the first interaction matrices obtained from it. Finally, in section 4, we discuss the limitations of the current setup, as well as some of the theoretical aspects of the Bi-O-Edge concept that requires further investigation.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This section describes our experimental setup.

2.1 Implementation principle

This section describes the technical implementation chosen to perform the Bi-O-Edge Fourier filtering. The Bi-O-Edge concept is extensively described in [10]. We only recall its key principles here. The Bi-O-Edge requires the formation of two focal spots, in each of which a Foucault Knife-Edge (FKE) test is performed along two orthogonal directions. Its defining feature is the replacement of the sharp edge of the classical FKE by a smooth intensity transition spanning a few diffraction diameters. This grey area width is chosen to be of the same order as the modulation radius of a modulated pyramid wavefront sensor, though the two parameters are not strictly equivalent. It is the key parameter governing the trade-off between sensitivity and dynamic range. In our implementation, the F-ratio at the Fourier plane is 66.7, the operating wavelength is 635 nm, and the grey area width is 240 μm , corresponding to $5.67 \lambda/D$.

The Bi-O-Edge mask we used has been provided to us by Sebastiaan Haffert, Frans Snik, and David Doelman from Leiden University. It allows to perform the above described filtering without losing photons. It consists of a patterned liquid crystal array that samples the focal plane with half-wave plates, each defined over an area of $10 \mu\text{m} \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ and with a spatially varying orientation, such as illustrated in fig. 2b. When linearly polarized light passes through a half-wave plate, its polarization direction is rotated by an angle determined by the orientation of the half-wave plate. This design therefore allows the polarization of the incoming light to be rotated by an amount that depends on its position in the focal plane.

Figure 1 illustrates how this component enables to perform the Bi-O-Edge filtering. The first Wollaston prism is used to both splits the light equally between the two focal planes we need to perform the Bi-O-Edge filtering and to provide the linearly polarized inputs required by the Bi-O-Edge mask. The Bi-O-Edge mask will then encode the amount of light to dispatch in each pupil by rotating the polarization direction of the light accordingly to its spatial coordinate: the light falling on about half of the focal plane remains with the same polarization orientation, the light falling on the other half gets its polarization direction rotated by 90° , and the light in the grey area gets rotated a given amount in between. Eventually, the second Wollaston prism acts as an analyser and effectively dispatch the light in 2 pupils per input channels, making four pupils on the detector.

Figure 1: Bi-O-Edge mask operation

2.2 Patterned liquid crystal array validation

This section describes the tests we performed on the patterned liquid crystal array before using it as the Bi-O-Edge mask. A macroscopic view of the component is shown in fig. 2a. The diameter of the substrate is 1 inch, allowing the component to be mounted in standard optical mounts.

Figure 2: The Bi-O-Edge mask and its visualization setup

To verify the mask geometry and behaviour, we used the setup shown in fig. 2c. It consists of a source that illuminates the full mask, two linear polarizers enclosing the mask, an imaging lens and a camera. The polarizer/analyser system allows us to visualize the half wave plates orientations, and therefore check the mask geometry and behaviour, as illustrated in fig. 3.

Figure 3: Bi-O-Edge mask observed between two linear polarizers. Each image is taken with a different orientation of the first polarizer

2.3 Hardware

The hardware we used and its main characteristics are presented in section 2.3.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Constructor	Thorlabs	Constructor	Meadowlark	Constructor	Hamamatsu
Model (laser)	S1FC635	Model	HSP1920-488-800-HSP8	Model	ORCA-Flash4.0 V2
Wavelength	635 nm	Resolution	1920 × 1152	Resolution	2048 × 2048
Fiber model	SM600	Pixel pitch	9.2 μm	Pixel pitch	6.5 μm
Fiber type	Single-mode	Extent	17.6 × 10.7 mm	Extent	13.312 × 13.312 mm
(a) Source		Stroke	2π rad	(c) Wavefront sensing camera	
		Encoding	256 (8-bit)		
		(b) SLM			

Table 1: Main hardware characteristics of the experimental setup.

2.4 Bench optical layout

This section describes our experimental setup. A schematic and a picture of the bench are shown in fig. 4.

(a) Bi-O-Edge bench optical layout

(b) Bi-O-Edge bench

Figure 4: The Bi-O-Edge prototype bench

3. PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we present the preliminary results achieved with the Bi-O-Edge prototype bench. We were able to acquire the firsts experimental interaction matrices. Our calibration basis consists of 342 KL modes, corresponding to approximately 20 actuators across the pupil diameter, computed with the OOPAO python package [4].

Both our SLM and our detector are largely oversampled, with respectively 660 and 576 pixels in the pupil diameter. This oversampled design allow us to characterize precisely our setup for any lower sampling by doing software binning, and do not cause any noise issue as we operate on an artificial source. It could be a limitation for the speed of the bench operations but in the current setup the speed limit is imposed by the SLM, that we are able to operate reliably only below 10 Hz.

We selected the valid pixels in our detector thanks to a basic thresholding. Each interaction matrix frame is computed by taking the difference between the flux-normalized push and pull signals (computed over valid pixels only), divided by the push-pull stroke amplitude in rad RMS. We used higher strokes and average the measurements over more frames for the low order modes than for the high order modes, taking care of staying within the sensor linear range (roughly below ± 0.3 rad RMS).

A visualization of the modal basis and an experimental interaction matrix for some calibration modes is shown in fig. 5.

The sensitivity of a wavefront sensor can be understood as the inverse of its noise propagation coefficients, as the more sensitive a wavefront sensor is, the less it will be impacted by noise. Sensitivity is, in most cases, different with respect to the photon noise or the readout noise [1]. We were able to compute the interaction

(a) Some calibration modes

(b) Some interaction matrix frames

Figure 5: Experimental interaction matrix visualization

matrix singular value decomposition as well as the experimental Bi-O-Edge modal sensitivities to photon noise, according to the formula introduced in [1]. These quantitative results are shown in fig. 6.

Both the SVD and the photon noise sensitivity curves show the expected shapes. Figure 6b demonstrate experimentally a performance level almost as good as the one predicted by the theory. However, we noticed that the experimental photon noise sensitivity for high orders modes is slightly below $\sqrt{2}$, the theoretical limit for a Foucault Knife Edge test.

The origin of this slight sensitivity deficit is not yet fully understood. We hypothesize that it may be attributable to the unfiltered zeroth order of the SLM, which carries a few percent of unmodulated light. This light contributes to the flux normalization without contributing to the wavefront signal, thereby artificially reducing the measured sensitivity. A cleaner test would be to repeat the measurements using Fourier modes rather than KL modes, eliminating any confounding effect from the multi-frequency (different frequency order and different orientation with respect to the knife edge) nature of our calibration modes. The theoretical sensitivity limit of $\sqrt{2}$ applies only to a pure high-order spatial frequency far from the Bi-O-Edge mask edges, making Fourier modes the appropriate basis for this validation.

(a) Singular value decomposition

(b) Photon noise sensitivity

Figure 6: Experimental interaction matrix quantitative analysis

4. CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

The Bi-O-Edge prototype bench already allowed us to validate in the lab part of the theoretical concept: the experimentally measured sensitivity is almost as good as the one expected by the theory. It has also been very useful to assess whether the technical implementation investigated here is suitable for future on-sky deployment.

Currently, we foresee two technical limitations that may prevent us to use this particular setup on sky. Both of them are related to the use of Wollaston prisms, and are illustrated in fig. 7.

1. Wollaston prisms are chromatic, their splitting angle is changing according to the wavelength. This may prevent accurate positioning of the mask across the full spectral bandwidth (first Wollaston prism), and may cause blurring of high spatial frequencies on the wavefront sensing camera (second Wollaston prism).
2. Wollaston prisms seems to introduce differential aberrations on each of their output channels, causing the four pupils to be focused at slightly different depths, and probably affected by astigmatism and distortion [8]. A single detector can therefore not be placed simultaneously at the optimal focal plane for all four pupils. In our prototype bench we manage to keep this effect small, but if this effect gets too pronounced in the optical design for on-sky tests, it might affect the quality of the measurements, as the extra propagation distance for each pupil is known to have both a non linear and a chromatic effect [9].

Figure 7: Illustrations of two Wollaston prisms related instrumental issues

Finally, some theoretical aspects around the Bi-O-Edge concept remains not fully understood. The static filtering of the Bi-O-Edge is not strictly equivalent to the dynamic modulation of the modulated pyramid, and a rigorous comparison of both sensors dynamic ranges needs to be established. Such a comparison is non-trivial, as the dynamic range of a wavefront sensor can be characterised in several ways — through linearity curves, optical gain estimates or full closed loop simulations. Furthermore, any meaningful comparison of sensitivity between two sensors must be made at equal dynamic range. To date, no set of parameters has been identified for which the Bi-O-Edge and the modulated pyramid can be considered to operate with the exact same dynamic range, which makes a direct sensitivity comparison difficult to carry out rigorously.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors are grateful to Sebastiaan Haffert, Frans Snik, and David Doelman from Leiden University for providing the patterned liquid crystal array used as the Bi-O-Edge Fourier mask in this work.

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